

Survey Protocol

This document presents the survey protocol. To achieve this, an exploratory survey was conducted to analyze and understand, based on the literature, how change management is handled in the context of software project management, as well as to understand the impact of these changes on software development. The survey was planned to follow the method proposed by Kasunic (2005), considering the field of software engineering. This document is divided into five parts: 1) Research Objectives; 2) Target Audience Identification; 3) Survey Instrument; 4) Survey Instrument Evaluation; 5) Data Collection and Analysis.

Research Objectives

We used the Goal-Question-Metric (GQM) model (Basili, 1984) to define the objectives of the study, which can be summarized as follows:

“Analyze changes management for the purpose of evaluation with respect to types, impacts, and communication from the point of view of professionals in the context of real software development projects.”

To achieve this objective, we aimed to investigate five Research Questions (RQs):

- **RQ1:** What is the profile of the professionals?
- **RQ2:** What are the professionals’ perceptions of the types of changes that have greatest impact on software development project?
- **RQ3:** What are the professionals’ perceptions of the impacts of changes on software development projects?
- **RQ4:** What are the professionals’ perceptions of the use of agile methodologies to help manage changes in software development projects?
- **RQ5:** What are the professionals’ perceptions of how changes are managed and communicated?

Target Audience Identification

The target audience of this research consists of professionals, bot men and women, with academic or industry experience in project management and/or change management in software development projects. These professionals are allocated in different companies and universities in Brazil and Portugal.

Survey Instrument Design

The survey was conducted using Microsoft Forms. The questionnaire, consisting of 39 questions, was designed based on Research Questions (RQs). It includes open-ended, multiple-choice, and single-choice questions. The structure is organized into five sections: (i) introduction to the survey, its objectives, and clarifications regarding response handling; (ii) collection of information on the academic background and professional experience of participants, focusing on project and change management, as well as the use of agile methodologies; (iii) identification of approaches used by professionals to deal with changes in projects; (iv) analysis of the effects of changes on the development cycle and suggestions for improving change management; (v) open field for observations and suggestions from participants.

To conduct an initial evaluation, three professionals (developer, professor, and project manager) from different levels and organizations were invited. The professor suggested the following improvements:

(i) making open-ended questions optional, allowing professional who truly wish to contribute to provide more precise answers; (ii) adding “Teacher/Researcher” as an option in the current job title field.

Data Collection and Analysis

After the pilot phase, the questionnaire was made available for professionals to respond. It was distributed via email to students of the Polytechnic Institute of Bragança (IPB) in Portugal, published on LinkedIn to request contributions, and shared with professionals close to the researchers through communication channels.

The questionnaire was launched on December 4, 2024, and as of March 26, 2025, it remains open for responses, with a total 31 responses recorded. The survey can be accessed at the following link: <https://forms.office.com/r/54UFAkFW6x?origin=lprLink>

The collected data is being analyzed and validated to ensure that responses from non-relevant professional profiles or inconsistent answers are disregarded and not counted in the research.

REFERENCES

- Kasunic, M. (2005). Designing an effective survey. Pittsburgh: Carnegie Mellon University.
- Basili, V. R. and Weiss, D. M. (1984). A Methodology for collecting valid software engineering data. IEEE Transactions on software engineering, (6): 728-738.